

Computed Tomography Evaluation of Renal Vascular Anatomy and Variations in an Omani Population

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Introduction

Renal vessels are known to show anatomical variations across different populations, and awareness of these variations is important in surgical and radiological practice. The present study aimed to evaluate the radiological anatomy of the renal arteries and veins in the Omani population, with particular focus on vessel diameter, laterality, and vascular branching patterns. Such data are important for preoperative planning, especially in renal transplantation, vascular interventions, and urologic surgery.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective cross-sectional study included adult patients aged 18 years and older who underwent contrast-enhanced computed tomography angiography of the abdomen and pelvis between 1 January 2023 and 31 December 2024. Normal CT angiograms performed for vascular pathology screening, renal transplant workup, or trauma evaluation with normal findings were included. The renal arteries and veins were assessed for diameter, anatomical course, and vascular variations. Accessory renal arteries were defined as any additional arteries arising directly from the aorta and supplying the kidney, regardless of the site of entry.

Results

A total of 128 patients were included. Accessory renal arteries were identified in 24.22% of patients (n = 31), including two cases with unilateral double accessory arteries. The mean diameters of the right and left renal arteries were 4.51 ± 0.91 mm and 4.95 ± 0.98 mm, respectively, and both were significantly larger in males ($p = 0.020$ and 0.026 , respectively). Supernumerary renal veins were observed in 21 patients, while retroaortic left renal vein and circumaortic left renal vein were identified in seven and one case, respectively. Overall, venous variations were identified in 17.2% of patients. The right renal vein was significantly larger in females ($p = 0.020$).

Conclusion

Renal vascular variations are not uncommon in the Omani population. These findings may contribute to improved preoperative imaging assessment and surgical planning in renal and retroperitoneal procedures.

Keywords

accessory; anatomy; CT; kidney; radiology; renal; artery; vein; variations